

Metal-Polyalkoxylate Complexes and their Applications in Analytical Potentiometry

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The complexation of polyalkoxylates with metals is discussed and preparation of tetraphenyl borates of the complexes summarized. The most appropriate methods for analyzing alkoxylates are based on their complexation reactions with metals in gravimetric, titrimetric and spectrophotometric procedures. Such reactions and the equilibrium between complexed metals and alkoxylates form the basis of membrane electrodes responding to various cations, especially with barium, lead and calcium ion selectivity, and to alkoxylates themselves. Among the applications for the barium and lead ion-selective electrodes are their use as endpoint indicators in the potentiometric titration of sulphate. The responses of the electrodes for polyalkoxylates may be used for evaluating critical micelle concentrations (CMCs) and analysis for these categories of non-ionic surfactants.

STRONG stoichiometric complexes of metal ions with neutral molecules have been observed only in recent years, the main interest being with biological materials and macrocyclic polyethers. The essential complexing principle is that these neutral organic molecules carry a sequence of localised charges (usually lone-pair electrons) of sufficient energy to form ion-dipole ligands with appropriate cations. The conformation of the molecule is such that it forms a solvation type shell around the cation, effectively replacing the ion hydration shell. The charged cationic complex thus formed is electrically balanced by anions.

Apart from the macrocyclic types of polyethers, there are the acyclic polyalkoxylates whose complexing tendencies with various cations and associated analytical connotations have been much studied in the author's laboratories and by others. It is appropriate, therefore, that fulfilment of the privileged invitation to contribute a paper for this Commemoration Volume in honour of the 60th birthday of Professor Arun K. Dey, should centre on these complexes, especially in view of the tremendous current interest in analytical chemistry circles of the whole field of complexation between metal ions and neutral molecules.

Nature of metal:alkoxylate complexes :

Polyalkoxylates are essentially acyclic polyethers with the $-(CH_2CH_2O)-$ repeating unit. They

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include polyethylene glycols (PEGs) $[HO(CH_2CH_2O)_nH]$, polyglycol dimethyl ethers (glymes) $[CH_3O-(CH_2CH_2O)_nCH_3]$, polypropylene glycols (PPGs) $[HO(CH(CH_3)CH_2O)_nH]$, and alkylphenoxypolyethoxy-

CH₃

lates of which the nonylphenoxypolyethoxylates (NPs) $[C_9H_{19}O(CH_2CH_2O)_nH]$ are typical.

The materials have various applications. For example, the low molecular mass PEGs are solvents, while the NPs are important non-ionic surfactants and variation in the number of ethoxylate units can produce useful changes in wetting, detergency, emulsification, solubility and foam properties.

It is appropriate to note the evolution of an understanding of the nature of these complexes. The polyelectrolyte properties of polyalkoxylates in the presence of metal ions suggested an association, as was confirmed by nmr studies of ion-dipole interactions between potassium iodide and polyethoxylate¹. Such interactions were, of course, evident from procedures for the analysis of alkoxylates. Also, there were the reaction between potassium alcoholate and polyalkoxylates²; spectrophotometric data on polyalkoxylates in the presence of sodium, potassium, and ammonium thiocyanates³; X-ray diffraction and other studies of complexes of mercury(II) halides with polyethoxylate^{4,5} and related ethoxylate oligomers⁶; and also the temperature-dependent optical and nmr spectroscopic data on the effectiveness of glymes as coordinating agents for alkali metal ions and for the ion pairs of fluorenyl carbonium alkali metal ion salts^{7,8}.

The tetraphenylborate salts of complexes between the NPs and other alkoxylates and alkaline earth and other metal cations, especially barium, have been exploited for their response in membrane electrode potentiometry⁹⁻²⁴. This has led to rather direct interest in synthesising salts of the complexes.

Of the several methods for obtaining polyalkoxylate adducts, the conversion with tetraphenylborate ions is very convenient and an extended range of the tetraphenylborates of cation complexes with PEGs, PPGs and NPs has been prepared in the author's laboratories. These are summarised in Table 1.

The preparative method is simple and straightforward^{15,25,26} and merely involves adding an

TABLE 1—TETRAPHENYLBORATES OF METAL CATION ADDUCTS OF POLYALKOXYLATES^{22, 24}

Polyalkoxylate	No. of AOU's	Stoichiometry of TPB precipitate	No. of AOU per cation	m.p. ^a °C
Antarox CO-880	30	Na(CO-880) _{0.28} .TPB	8.4	98-100
		Mg(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	40-45 with decomposition
		Ca(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	185-190
		Sr(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	197-200
		Ba(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	215-217
		Cu(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	(Ref. 26)
		Pb(CO-880) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	very unstable 12.0	(Ref. 26)
Antarox CO-890	40	Na(CO-890) _{0.21} .TPB	8.4	108-110
		Mg(CO-890) _{0.2} .TPB ₂	12.0	60-65
		Ba(CO-890) _{0.2} .TPB ₂	12.0	207-220
Antarox CO-850	20	Na(CO-850) _{0.42} .TPB	8.4	55-60 with decomposition
		Ba(CO-850) _{0.4} .TPB ₂	12.0	210-215
PEG (1540)	34	Na(PEG-1540) _{0.24} .TPB	8.5	150-155
		Mg(PEG-1540) _{0.21} .TPB ₂	10.5	135-138
		Ba(PEG-1540) _{0.21} .TPB ₂	10.5	225-230
PPG (1025)	17.36	Na(PPG-1025) _{0.4} .TPB	8.5	-
		Mg(PPG-1025) _{0.66} .TPB ₂	12.0	-
		Ca(PPG-1025) _{0.66} .TPB ₂	12.0	70-75
		Sr(PPG-1025) _{0.66} .TPB ₂	12.0	105-110
		Ba(PPG-1025) _{0.66} .TPB ₂	12.0	140-145
PPG (2025)	34.56	Ca(PPG-2025) _{0.26} .TPB ₂	12.0	60-65
		Sr(PPG-2025) _{0.26} .TPB ₂	12.0	60-65
		Ba(PPG-2025) _{0.26} .TPB ₂	12.0	55-60

^a Poor stability and decomposition where m.p. data are not given [except for Pb(CO-880)_{0.4}.TPB₂ where m.p. was not determined]. All the m.ps. are irreversible with signs of charring at 5° below the minimum of the quoted ranges.

aqueous metal chloride solution (nitrate for lead) (10 cm³ of 0.1M or 1M solution) to an aqueous solution (0.154 g 100 cm⁻³) of the appropriate polyalkoxylate (NP, PEG or PPG). The resulting oxonium ion may be precipitated with excess sodium TPB (10⁻³M), filtered, washed well with water and vacuum dried at 35-50°.

The waxy, thermally unstable magnesium and copper complexes need to be dried over phosphorus pentoxide.

Although the same general method applies to the TPB salts of sodium complexes, concentrated sodium chloride solutions (1M) are needed to coagulate the precipitates prior to final drying over phosphorus pentoxide.

Analytical and spectroscopic characterisation of the white products (pale blue for the copper complex) were in accord^{25, 26} for the complexes summarised in Table 1. The number of alkoxy units (AOU) per cation (Table 1) calculated from nmr spectra was deduced from the total number of protons of the alkoxy chain of each complex molecule as determined from the height of their integrated area in the nmr spectrum in relation to integrations of the TPB protons which were shifted far downfield from those of the alkoxy protons²⁵. Due allowance was made for the phenyl protons associated with the NPs when deducing the number of TPBs associated with each polymer molecule of predetermined molecular mass²⁵.

The number of alkoxy units associated with each metal ion obtained from nmr data in the above way was found to be similar to values obtained by chemical analysis. For the NP adducts with bivalent cations, the assessment of 12 alkoxy units per cation fully supports earlier assessments for calcium, strontium and barium complexes, respectively^{9, 11, 27}. For the PEG complexes, the previously reported ratio of ≈ 10.5 alkoxy units per bivalent cation²⁸ has also been found to hold. The alkoxy:sodium ratios for the complexes in Table 1 are close to the figure of 8 required to wrap the sodium ion completely in order to promote maximum stability^{29, 30}.

Analysis of alkoxyates :

Coordination reactions between alkoxyates and metal cations form the basis of gravimetric, titrimetric and spectrophotometric analytical procedures for alkoxyates²² (Table 2). Of these, the spectrophotometric methods are the most appropriate to date for analysing alkoxyate non-ionic surfactants in waters and effluents²². For the sake of completeness, certain other methods for analysing alkoxyates are included in Table 2.

Membrane electrodes with sensors of polyalkoxylate metal adducts :

Ion-sensing :

Several of the complexes listed in Table 1 form the basis of successful sensors in liquid⁹⁻¹² and

TABLE 2—METHODS OF ANALYSING ALKOXYLATES

Method type	Brief description	Reference
Gravimetry	Precipitation of metal ion : alkoxyate complex with potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) potassium tetraiodobismuthate(III) heteropolyacids sodium tetraphenylborate	31 32-34 35-39 40-44
Titrimetry	Metal ion : alkoxyate complex titrated with sodium tetraphenylborate using various methods of end-point detection, including visual indicator (Congo Red) ^{16,17} , potentiometry (with silver indicator electrode ²⁰), indirect coulometry with biamperometric detection ⁴⁶ and thermometric titration ⁴⁷	27, 28 45-47
Spectrophotometry	Solvent extraction of complexes of polyalkoxylates with metal ions using large polarisable ions like tetrathioisocyanatocobaltate(II) at 620 nm heteropolyacid (molybdenum complex at $\approx$ 650 nm) picrate (at 378 nm)	48-53 54 15, 55-58
Chromatography (GLC and TLC)	GLC may be used for lower polyalkoxylates by direct methods ^{59,60,67} ; cleavage methods may also be employed ^{60,61} . TLC may be used for higher, slightly volatile, oligomers ^{60,63,66} .	59-67
Spectroscopy	UV ^{50,68} and ir ^{50,69,70} . X-ray fluorescence ^{69,70}	15, 68-70
Indirect spectrophotometry	Solvent extraction into 1,2-dichlorobenzene of neutral adduct of non-ionic surfactant with potassium tetrathioisocyanatozincate(II). Zinc(II) in the extract determined spectrophotometrically after adding 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol and triethanolamine	71

PVC matrix membrane^{18-19,24} ion-selective electrodes. A successful barium ion-selective electrode system^{18,24} is based on the complex of a nonylphenoxypolyethoxyate containing 12 ethoxyate units and 2 mol of tetraphenylborate ion per mole of barium ions [Ba(Antarox CO-880)_{0.4}.TPB₂]. For use in PVC matrix membrane electrodes, this requires a more viscous solvent mediator than the 4-nitroethylbenzene used in liquid membrane electrodes¹⁸. Both 2-nitrophenyl phenyl ether and 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether satisfy this condition, but the former gives electrodes of superior lifetimes (about 30 days).

PVC matrix membrane electrodes¹⁸ based on [Ba(Antarox CO-880)_{0.4}.TPB₂] sensor and 2-nitrophenyl phenyl ether solvent mediator have effective linear calibration ranges of 10⁻¹ to $\approx$ 10⁻⁵ M barium ions, near-Nernstian slopes of 28 to 29 mV decade⁻¹, response times of less than 1 min in normal ranges and $\approx$ 5 min near the detection limit, daily drifts of only 1 to 2 mV and long effective pH ranges (1.5 to 10). Selectivity coefficients, $k_{B,A}^{pot}$, for barium over a large range of ions, B, (interferent, [B]=10⁻¹ M) are less than 1.8 $\times$ 10⁻² for B=Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ni, or Cu.

Among the possible applications of these PVC matrix membrane electrodes is the potentiometric titration of sulphate with barium ions. Such titrations of 10⁻¹ and 10⁻² M solutions of sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid with barium chloride and using the electrode with a calomel reference electrode¹⁸ gave a coefficient of variation corresponding to the theoretical end-point of 0.1%. The break in emf at the end-point for the titration of 1.56 mg of sulphur from sulphate in 15 cm³ solution exceeds 50 mV. Titrations of the sulphate following oxygen flask combustions of dibenzyl sulphide, S-benzylthiuronium chloride, dibenzyl sulphide+aniline phosphate (5+3) and triphenylphosphonic sulphide

gave average sulphur recoveries of 100.25 per cent, thus confirming the technique as a possible application for the barium ion-selective electrode¹⁸.

Other potentiometric titration applications of the barium ion-selective electrode are the titration of sulphate in the presence of chromium(VI)²⁴ and in the determination of sulphate in sea water and certain natural waters with liquid membrane electrode⁷². The electrode has also been tested for determining sulphate by analate subtraction⁷³.

In titration work, regard must be had to possible interferences by cations and anions. In this respect, cations, for example potassium, which can be sensed by the barium ion-selective electrode, give distorted titration curves, while pH values below 1.5 led to electrode breakdown¹⁸. Cations, such as calcium, which interact with sulphate give low sulphate recovery, while anions that interact with the barium titrant lead to apparently high sulphate. Treatment of samples with cation-exchange resins in the sodium form can remove cation interferences, while acidification to pH 2 with hydrochloric acid prevents interference from anions, such as phosphate, carbonate, hydrogen carbonate and organic anions¹⁸.

Bauman¹² has successfully used a liquid membrane electrode based on the tetraphenylborate of the strontium-NP (30 ethoxyate units) complex for strontium ion determinations, but naturally barium was absent in these samples.

Tetraphenylborates of sodium and alkaline earth metal ion-complexes with a polypropoxyate [PPG(1025)] have been evaluated for ion-selective electrode qualities in conjunction with various solvent mediators^{16,17}. From these a creditable PVC matrix-membrane calcium ion-selective electrode evolved. This was functional over a wide pH range (4.5 to > 10) and was based on the Ca(PPG-1025)_{0.60}.TPB₂ of Table 1 as sensor

and dioctylphenyl phosphonate as solvent mediator. Since the sensor starting materials are noted for their properties and as non-ionic surfactants or for altering the humectant properties of simple glycols and glycerine, they are readily available. This and the ease with which they can be complexed with certain cations, calcium in this case, and precipitated as tetraphenylborates render the sensors readily accessible for ion-selective electrode construction¹⁷. This can be advantageous when the, evidently much better, calcium ion-selective electrodes based on the more difficult to prepare organophosphate and neutral carrier sensor systems⁷⁴ are not at hand or if their enhanced selectivity is not required.

Alkoxyrate sensing :

The barium ion-selective electrodes discussed above may be used in a converse potentiometric approach for sensing alkoxyrates in solution¹⁹. The observed potentiometric response is an increase of up to ≈ 100 mV in emf of the barium versus a calomel reference electrode according to the amount of added alkoxyrate in the $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $10^{-8} M$ range. The response is linear with $\log[\text{alkoxyrate}]$, but is characterised¹⁹ by a break in the linearity which is attributed to the critical micelle concentration (CMC).

The alkoxyrate potentiometric response has been observed¹⁹ for various members of the AntaroX series of NPs, namely, CO-430 (n=4), CO-630 (n=9), CO-730 (n=15), CO-850 (n=20), CO-880 (n=30) and CO-890 (n=40). Other materials for which the response has been observed¹⁹ include AntaroX CA-620 and Triton X-100 (both are octylphenoxypolyethoxylates), Tween 80 (a sorbitan-9-octadecanoatepolyethoxylate) and several alkylpolyethoxylates (Dobanol 27-7, Lutensol AO7 and Synperonic 7). It is interesting to observe the good comparison between experimental (by electrode) literature and the calculated CMC for members of the AntaroX series of NPs (Table 3).

TABLE 3—CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATIONS OF ANTAROX NPs¹⁹

AntaroX	Critical micelle concentration $10^{-4} M$		
	Experimental by electrode	Literature	Calculated ^c in $CMC = \frac{A}{n+B}$
CO-890	4.6 (0.38 sd)	—	4.5
CO-880	2.5 (0.24)	2.5 to 3.0 ^a 1.85 ^b	2.6
CO-850	1.4 (0.26)	1.35 to 1.75 ^a 1.40 ^b	1.5
CO-730	1.1 (0.056)	1.0 to 1.30 ^a 1.10 ^b	1.11
CO-630	0.83 (0.074)	—	0.80
CO-430	0.60 (0.055)	—	0.60

^a Hsiao, Dunning and Lorenz, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 657.
^b Schick, Atlas and Eirich, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1326.
^c Equation obtained from Reference ^a with $A = 0.056$ and $B = 3.87$.

Later research has shown that electrodes where the TPB of the barium complex of AntaroX CO-880 in the membrane has been replaced by the TPB of the barium complex of AntaroX CO-430, are superior in their response to the non-ionic polyalkoxyrates mentioned above. This indicates a further possible application for these electrochemical sensors, for polyalkoxyrates are widely used as non-ionic surfactants^{22,75}.

The AntaroX CO-430 electrode has been evaluated²⁰ for determining Dobanol 25-7, Synperonic 7 and Lutensol AO7 in detergent powder solutions of concentration 0.15% m/v (equivalent to $\approx 0.015\%$ m/v or 150 ppm of the non-ionic surfactant). The recommended procedure is based on known (standard) addition²⁰. In this test, 25 cm³ of 0.15% fully-formulated detergent solutions, containing the non-ionic surfactant being determined, were spiked with non-ionic surfactant of known concentration²⁰. Data obtained for AntaroX CO-430 electrodes, calibrated by adding aliquots of Synperonic 7 solutions (1.0% m/v) to 25 cm³ of a 0.15% m/v aqueous solution of fully formulated detergent base, are quoted in Table 4.

With regard to more general application, there will be many situations when alkoxyrates will

TABLE 4—SOME KNOWN ADDITION DATA OF POLYALKOXYLATE TYPE NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS IN SOLUTIONS OF MODEL AND REAL SAMPLES OF DETERGENT POWDERS DETERMINED BY ANTAROX CO-430 ELECTRODE AND USING SYNPERONIC 7 SPIKES (ADAPTED FROM REF. 20)

Nature of sample and of polyalkoxyrate (all in fully formulated detergent base) in deionised water	Non-ionic surfactant in solution/% m/v			(n)
	Expected	Found	s.d/ 10^{-4}	
Synperonic 7 (model power)	0.0150 ^a	0.0151	1.2	(5)
Dobanol 25-7 plus (model)	0.0150	0.0150	1.7	(5)
Synperonic 7 (1+1) (powder)	0.0150	0.0150	1.7	(5)
Synperonic 7 (model powder)	0.0080	0.0079	0.8	(4)
Synperonic 7 (model powder)	0.0320	0.0321	5.4	(4)
Fully formulated detergent powder 'A' containing Lutensol AO7	0.0150	0.0146	2.5	(15)
Fully formulated detergent powder 'B' containing a non-ionic surfactant of unspecified alkyl	0.0150	0.0150	1.4	(12)

^a: 0.0150% m/v = 150 ppm

be present at considerably lower levels than the examples of Table 4. In this respect, it should be noted that the Antarox CO-430 electrode will respond to less than 0.15 mg dm^{-2} ($10^{-7} M$) of Antarox CO-880 in deionised water²⁰, but it is a pity that the electrode response times are so long ($\approx 30 \text{ min}$) at such low levels of alkoxylate.

Conclusion :

Complexes between metal ions and polyalkoxylates offer a new interesting area of study in chemistry of such considerable practical application that they also merit study with regard to ion-dipole interactions and structure, by those who are more theoretically oriented. The information so obtained can then be used to plan improved systems that can be applied to obtain better sensors and analytical methods and to enhance the use of these materials as selective extractants for metal ions.

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